

Results

As the concentration of nitric acid is increased from 3.0*N* to 4.0*N*, the actual loss in weight of 63/37 brass decreases showing the improvement in the performance of the inhibitor with an increase in nitric acid concentration.

Compared to *N*-methyl aniline, *N,N'*-dimethyl aniline is a less satisfactory inhibitor. At low inhibitor concentrations, it accelerates the corrosion of 63/37 brass in 2.0*N* nitric acid (Table 1).

Event at 4.35 ml/l concentration *N*, ethyl aniline gives nearly complete protection to 63/37 brass in 2.0*N* nitric acid (Table 1). Compared to *N*, methyl aniline *N*, ethyl aniline is a better inhibitor to 2.0*N* and 3.0*N* nitric acid.

Compared to *N*-ethyl aniline, *N,N'*-diethyl aniline is an unsatisfactory inhibitor (Table 1).

With all the alkylanilines, the corrosion potential shifts in the negative direction which may suggest the preferential effect of these inhibitors on local cathodes. This is confirmed by polarization measurements. These inhibitors increase cathode polarization considerably as compared to the anode polarization (Fig. 2)

Discussion

The corrosive attack of nitric acid on brass is due to the autocatalytic formation of nitrous acid. It has been suggested that any substance which breaks the autocatalytic cycle of formation of nitrous acid can act as an inhibitor, and thus the inhibitive action of aromatic amines may be due to their diazotization action. Our previous work on primary amines in general confirms this hypothesis.

If the action of aromatic amines is only due to diazotization and subsequent removal of HNO₂, secondary amines like *N*-methylamine and *N*-ethyl aniline should be mediocre inhibitors and the tertiary amines like *N,N'*-dimethyl aniline and *N,N'*-diethylaniline should not act as inhibitors for the corrosion of 63/37 brass in nitric acid. The results obtained in the present investigations with *N,N'*-dimethylaniline and *N'*-methyl aniline are in agreement with the above presumption in that *N*-methyl aniline is a mediocre inhibitor, but *N,N'*-dimethylaniline fails to act as an inhibitor. However, both *N*-ethylaniline and *N,N'*-diethylaniline are satisfactory inhibitors for the corrosion of 63/37 brass in

nitric acid, which suggests that the diazotization of amine and the consequent removal of nitrous acid is not the only reason for the protectivity of aromatic amine. Amines can react with protons to form onium ions, which may be adsorbed on metal surface and protect it from corrosive attack of the acid. The present work indicates that the inhibition of the corrosion of brass in nitric acid is a complex phenomenon concerned with the removal of nitrous acid from the medium as well as with the adsorption of aromatic amines on the metal surface. Probably with the lengthening of the side chain attached to the nitrogen atom, the adsorption characteristics of the amines improve, resulting in more effective inhibitive action.

Reference

1. M. N. DESAI, Y. C. SHAH and M. H. GANDHI, *Corrosion Science*, 1969, 9, 65.

Benzothiazole Derivatives : Part VII. Synthesis of Some *N*-(2-Benzothiazolyl)anthranilic Acids as Potential Antiinflammatory Agents

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N-ARYLANTHRANILIC acids (fenamic acids) constitute an important class of compounds exhibiting antiinflammatory activity¹. This property is also shared by some of their heterocyclic analogues². In view of the antiinflammatory activity exhibited by several benzothiazole derivatives described in patent literature³ and in the light of our experience with some antiinflammatory benzothiazole compounds synthesised in our laboratory⁴, we decided to synthesise some *N*-(2-benzothiazolyl) anthranilic acids (I) for evaluation as antiinflammatory agents.

R = H, Cl, NO₂
 R₁ = H, Cl, Br
 R₂ = H, Br.

N-(2-Benzothiazolyl)anthranilic acids substituted in benzothiazole as well as in anthranilic acid moieties were prepared according to the method of Katz⁵ by the hydrolysis of 12*H*-benzothiazolo [2,3-*b*]quinazolin-12-ones (II), which were obtained by the reaction of 2-chlorobenzothiazoles with various anthranilic acids. Attempts to esterify the anthranilic acids (I) with ethanol in presence of conc. sulphuric acid resulted in the cyclisation to the respective benzothiazoloquinazolinone (II).

IR spectra of all the benzothiazoloquinazolinones (II) showed a characteristic absorption at $\sim 1695\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C=O) whereas those of benzothiazolyl anthranilic acids (I) were typical of *N*-arylanthranilic acids with peaks in the regions 3100 cm^{-1} (NH), $2700\text{--}2400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (bonded OH) and 1700 cm^{-1} (C=O).

The NMR spectrum of I, R = R₁ = R₂ = H, displayed NH and COOH protons as a broad signal at $\delta 10.7$ (2H) which disappeared on shaking with D₂O. The considerable down field shift observed for NH proton may be due to the zwitterion character of I. A broad multiplet at $\delta 7.0$ to 8.8 integrated for 8 aromatic protons. NMR spectrum of compound I, R = R₂ = H, R₁ = Br, had a similar pattern with signals at $\delta 11.3$ (broad, 2H NH and COOH) and $\delta 7.2\text{--}8.7$ (multiplet, 7H aromatic).

Mass spectrum of compound I, R = R₁ = R₂ = H, displays a moderate molecular ion peak at *m/e* 270 (20%). The base peak of the spectrum (A; *m/e* 252) arose from the loss of H₂O through a six-membered transition state involving adjacent NH and COOH groups, a conclusion which is further supported by the appearance of a metastable peak at *m/e* 235. This decomposition parallels with "ortho effects" observed with 2-methylbenzoic acid⁶ and ethyl 3-hydroxythiophene-2-carboxylate⁷. The ion A then loses the elements of CO and HCN, the latter presumably via a skeletal rearrangement⁸ giving peaks at *m/e* 224 (16%) and *m/e* 225 (20%), respectively.

The mass spectral fragmentation of I, R = R₂ = H, R₁ = Br, is analogous to that observed with I, R = R₁ = R₂ = H showing peaks at *m/e* 348/350 (parent peak), *m/e* 330/332 (base peak), 302/304 and 303/305.

Preliminary pharmacological screening of a few compounds showed that they possess low to moderate antiinflammatory activity, the highest activity was observed in compound I, R = R₂ = H, R₁ = Br, which showed inhibition of 28% carrageenin rat paw oedema test⁹ at dose level of 60 mg/kg.

Experimental

All the melting points were taken in open capillary in sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in nujol mulls with a Beckman IR-20 Spectrophotometer. NMR spectra were recorded for solutions in DMSO-d₆ on a T-60 instrument with TMS as internal standard. Mass spectra were obtained with an A.E.I MS 902 mass spectrometer.

2-Chloro-, 2-chloro-6-nitro-, and 2,6-dichloro-benzothiazoles were prepared by known methods¹⁰. Substituted anthranilic acids were obtained by procedures already reported¹¹.

12*H*-Benzothiazolo [2,3-*b*]quinazolin-12-ones (II). Appropriate 2-chlorobenzothiazole (0.03 mole) and the corresponding anthranilic acid (0.03 mole) were dissolved in glacial acetic acid (50 ml) and the mixture heated under reflux for 45 min. The resulting solution deposited a crystalline solid on cooling which was filtered, washed with methanol, dried and crystallised from a suitable solvent. The compounds thus prepared are listed in Table 1 along with their analytical and physical data.

N-(2-Benzothiazolyl)anthranilic acids (I). A mixture of 12*H*-benzothiazolo [2,3-*b*]quinazolin-12-one (II, 0.02 mole), potassium hydroxide (0.05 mole) and methanol (50%, 100 ml) was heated under reflux for 3 hr. The resultant solution was cooled in ice and acidified with 6*N* hydrochloric acid (congo red). The solid product was filtered, washed with water until free from acid, dried, and crystallised from an appropriate solvent. The compounds thus prepared and their physical and analytical data are listed in Table 2.

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TABLE 1—12H-BENZOTHAZOLO [2, 3-b] QUINAZOLIN-12-ONES (II)

Sr. No.	R	R ₁	R ₂	Solvent of Crystallisation	m.p. °C	Yield %	Analytical Data	
							Found S	Required S
1.	H	H	H	Toluene-Cyclohexanone (lit ⁵ . m.p. 193)	193	90	—	—
2.	H	Br	H	Toluene	225*	69	9.31	9.67
3.	H	H	Br	Toluene	222	67	9.32	9.67
4.	Cl	Br	H	Dioxane	220	65	8.31	8.75
5.	Cl	H	Br	Toluene	222	68	8.32	8.75
6.	NO ₂	H	H	DMF	290	75	10.49	10.78
7.	NO ₂	Br	H	Dioxane	>300	60	8.25	8.51
8.	NO ₂	H	Br	Dioxane	>300	60	8.21	8.51
9.	NO ₂	Cl	H	DMF	>300	60	9.19	9.65

*N; Found 7.96, Calcd. 8.46. Molecular weight by mass spectrometry 330/332. Kaushal *et al.*¹² reported m.p. 182°.

TABLE 2—N-(2-BENZOTHAZOLYL)-ANTHRANILIC ACIDS (I)

Sr. No.	R	R ₁	R ₂	Solvent of Crystallisation	m.p. °C	Yield %	Analytical Data			
							Found S	Found N	Required S	Required N
1.	H	H	H	Toluene	194 (Lit ⁵ . m.p. 195)	98	—	—	—	—
2.	H	Br	H	Toluene	210	58	8.81	7.55	9.17	8.02
3.	H	H	Br	Dioxane	208	67	8.88	7.61	9.17	8.02
4.	Cl	Br	H	Toluene	215	50	7.97	6.85	8.34	7.30
5.	Cl	H	Br	Toluene	228	60	8.03	6.95	8.34	7.00
6.	NO ₂	H	H	Dioxane	>300	66	9.88	—	10.16	—
7.	NO ₂	Br	H	DMF	>300	40	7.58	—	8.12	—
8.	NO ₂	H	Br	DMF	>300	50	7.64	—	8.12	—
9.	NO ₂	Cl	H	DMF	>300	55	8.86	—	9.15	—

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